

UNIVERSITY OF GHANA

CORPORATE BRAND AND BRAND VALUATION METHODS IN GHANA

A CASE STUDY OF LISTED BANKS IN GHANA

BY

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**A LONG ESSAY SUBMITTED TO THE DEPARTMENT OF ACCOUNTING, UNIVERSITY OF GHANA
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DECLARATION

I do hereby declare that this work is the result of my own research and has not been presented by anyone for any academic award in this or any other university. All references used in the work have been fully acknowledged.

I bear sole responsibility for any shortcomings.

.....

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.....

DATE

CERTIFICATION

I hereby certify that this long essay was supervised in accordance with the procedures laid down by the University.

.....

DR. CLETUS AGYENIM-BOATENG

.....

DATE

DEDICATION

This study is dedicated to the following people.

My mum, Mrs. Jemima Essilfie Tano, who all through my life has been a source of strength, instilling in me the will and discipline to face all of life's challenges in whatever form they may come.

My friends, Jeffery Walters Okusu, Emeli Akuaku Dzakpasu and Albert Douglas Quayson, who have inspired and helped me in the collation of this study.

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ABBREVIATIONS

CAR: Capital Adequacy Ratio

IAS: International Accounting Standard

IAS 36: Impairment of Assets

IAS 38: Intangible Assets

IFRS: International Financial Reporting Standard

IFRS 3: Business Combinations

ISO: International Organization for Standardization

ISO 10668:2010: Monetary Brand Valuation

OECD: Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development.

SOFP: Statement of Financial Position

ABSTRACT

Background and Purpose: The world today has made us increasingly aware of the importance of branded products, services and corporations; hence, a brand if managed well, can be a very valuable asset for the growth and success of any company. However, many companies face the challenge of assigning a monetary value to these brands in order to present them in their fair values, in their statement of financial position. Thus, this study seeks to ascertain the various intangible assets recognized by the various banks on the Ghana Stock Exchange (GSE) as well as how these banks, initially recognize, measure and disclose both financial and non-financial information in their Statement of Financial Information (SOFP).

Approach/Design/Methodology: Primary data would be collected through qualitative interviews via a set of survey questions set out in the form of questionnaires; while secondary data is collected from articles, literatures in journals and the internet. Furthermore, the data is analyzed by using the thematic approach.

Findings: Based on the data collected, the specific intangible assets including brand assets, recognized and disclosed by the listed banks are determined; as well as their underlying recognition criteria, measurement and disclosures.

Originality/Significance: There is no current research performed in the Ghanaian context, in relation to the research topic. Thus, it seeks to add to the existing literature on the subject matter in the context of developing economies.

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Introduction

This section gives a general overview of the research topic as well as the challenges encountered by the various listed banks in accounting for their intangible assets, specifically, their brand assets.

1.1.1 Background

Historically, the concept of branding involved the art of creating symbols or marks on livestock and timber to depict the maker or one's ownership of such items (Bastos & Levy, 2012; McDonough & Egolf, 2015; Percy, 2003). Thus, the Interbrand Group (1992) defined a brand to be the unique identity of an asset. Furthermore, the term brand brought about the transition from showing proof of ownership, to the patronage of products and services with well-known and established names and or symbols (Bastos & Levy, 2012), efficient lines of production, distribution and promotion (Moorhouse, 1989) as well as the quality and characteristics they possess (Boundless, 2015; Svanberg & Maxén, 2014).

Corporate brands fall into the category of intangible assets to which IAS 38 defines as “identifiable, non-monetary asset without physical substance held for use in the production or supply of goods or services, for rental to others, or for administrative purposes” and which depicts the unique identity of a company, giving it some form of competitive edge, over its competitors.

Additionally, intangible assets can be classified into two major groups; dependent on the manner in which they are acquired and further grouped based on their life span. The intangible assets further grouped into their life span, is done in order to determine their subsequent

measurement, as illustrated in Table 1 (Zéghal & Anis, 2011). Furthermore, based on the information provided in the Table 1, one will realize that, brands are not just market-related assets (Brooking, 1996; Rodov & Leliaert, 2002), but also, have an indefinite-life and no probable end in their ability to deliver cash flows. However, unlike tangible assets, expenditures incurred in the development and maintenance of intangible assets with indefinite-life (Brands) are not capitalized but directly expensed in the period in which they are incurred (Austin, 2007; Hùegh-Krohn & Knivsfila, 2000).

To illustrate, let us assume that the trademark gained in the acquisition of The Trust Bank (TTB) by Ecobank Ghana is used to efficiently expand the customer-base of Ecobank Ghana. Indicating that, the expanded services rendered would generate future cash flows for the unforeseeable future (accorded to the Going Concern principle). In this case, the brand name is said to have an indefinite life due to its ability to generate future cash flows.

Table 1: Categorization of intangible assets

Types of Intangible	Manner Acquired		Amortization	Impairment Test
	Externally Acquired	Internally Generated		
Limited-Life Intangible	Capitalize	Expense*	Over useful life	Recoverability test, then fair value test.
Indefinite-Life Intangible	Capitalize	Expense*	Do not amortize	Fair Value Test

*Except for direct costs such as legal costs.

1.1.2. The Role of Corporate Brands

Some analysts see brands as the major enduring asset of a company that outlasts the company's specific product and facilities (Kotler, Armstrong, Wong, & Saunders, 2010) to which the former CEO of MacDonal'd's, Jack Greenberg, agreed with when he indicated that, "*If every asset we own, every building and every piece of equipment were destroyed in a terrible natural disaster, we would be able to borrow all the money to replace it very quickly because of the value of our brand...the brand is more valuable than the totality of all these assets*".

Furthermore, brands serve as an indispensable part in an organization's ability to foster a long lasting relationship with its customers. They also represent the collection of feelings and perceptions about quality, image, lifestyle and status that a product or service creates in their minds. In other words, a brand that is able to substantially influence the minds of customers is what Kotler and Armstrong (2008) term as brand equity. According to IAS 38, a brand can be defined as an asset that does not have physical existence (Otonkue, Ezak, & Edu, 2009) and the value of which cannot be determined exactly unless it becomes a subject of a specific business transaction of sale and acquisition (Seetharaman, Nadzir, & Gunalan, 2001; Zéghal & Anis, 2011).

It should be noted that, brand equity and brand value depict dissimilar theories and should therefore, not be used interchangeably (Leone & Reggio, 2008). Brand equity according Investopedia (2015), is the positive association that customers already have with a particular brand that would affect their decision to purchase other products or services under that same brand name, rather than any other brand. Inasmuch as a brand with high brand equity is considered to be a very valuable asset (Kotler, Burton, & Deans, 2012; Masterson & Pickton, 2010), the power and value it holds might vary in the marketplace, depending on the extent to

which it is able to fulfill its promise of benefits to customers (Leone & Reggio, 2008) and the level of forged connections these customers have with that brand (Kotler et al., 2010). Moreover, in measuring brand equity a number of non-financial measures or factors such as brand awareness, brand loyalty and perceived quality of brand are used to determine the overall value of the brand – Brand Value (Seetharaman et al., 2001; Seetharaman, Nadzir, & Gunalan, 2006).

Brand value is therefore defined as the extra sum customers are willing to pay for the premium accruing to a brand (Business Dictionary, 2015) as well as the net present value (NPV) of the estimated cash flows attributable to that brand (Brand Finance, 2015). Leone and Reggio (2008) and Kirk, Ipshita, and Wilson (2012) share the opinion that, brand value is the sale or replacement price of a brand. The definitions propounded for brand values above, are in agreement with that of IAS 38, where it is stated that, the brand's value can only be capitalized and accounted for if it forms a part of a business combination, as directed by IFRS 3 – Business Combination. Furthermore, some authors (Austin, 2007; Gilbertson & Preston, 2005; Seetharaman et al., 2006; Svanberg & Maxén, 2014) are of the view that, brand values should be accounted for over time and set against an active market to ascertain the performance of that brand and how it affects both the financial and non-financial performance of the company which this study seeks to find out.

Additionally, until 2010, when the ISO 10668 came up with a set of standardized monetary brand valuation techniques, firms were allowed to use other methods which best suites their interests; thus, creating an uneven basis of comparison between firms' brand values, even, within the same industry. Now, due to the conservatism principle, firms with banks inclusive, are unable to capitalize their brand values.

This study therefore, seeks to ascertain why intangible asset values (brands) are inadequately accounted for and how it affects the performance of Ghanaian listed banks. It also focuses on the recognition criteria, initial and subsequent measurement and disclosure of brands and intangible assets in general, in the SOFP of banks.

The remainder of this chapter is organized as follows: Section 1.2 brings out the problem statement which has the research questions to be addressed, inculcated within, as well as Section 1.3, showing the significance of the study.

1.2 Problem Statement

The growing interests in the recognition, valuation and disclosure of brand values on the face of a company's SOFP, can be dated back to the 1980's. There have been lots of studies in that field of study to help better understand the incessant interest in the study area (Otonkue et al., 2009; Salinas & Ambler, 2009; Stolowy, Haller, & Klockhaus, 2001; Tollington, 1999; Zéghal & Anis, 2011). Yet, irrespective of the various international standards set to address issues on brands, some gaps can still be identified in literature.

First, very little studies have been done in the developing countries. The geographic context within which brands have been typically researched into, are mostly the European countries and the United States of America. Former CEO of Quaker Oats, John Stewart states that, *"If this business was split up, I would give you the land and bricks and mortar, and I would keep the brands and trademarks, and I would fare better than you"*. This indicates that the relevance of a strong brand to the growth prospects of every company (OECD, 2006a, 2006b), is crucial; hence, most of the banks in developing countries are now particular about their brand and how it affects their performance in attracting foreign investments, which inadvertently improves the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of most, if not all developing countries.

Secondly, the focus of the study of brands is mostly directed towards that of customer-related assets, rather than financial assets (Andersen & Striukova, 2004; Austin, 2007; Keller, 1993). Some authors stipulate that, the measurement and presentation of information on brands as a financial asset is usually of very little importance to an investor. Austin (2007) and Zéghal and Anis (2011) are of the opinion that, the measurement and presentation of information on the values of brands are not an end in itself, but are used in strategically managing the affairs of the company using the components of brands as non-financial performance measures.

Finally, many studies have been conducted on the intellectual capital and Research and Development (R&D) aspects of the subject of intangible assets (Al-Musali & Ismail, 2014; Andersen & Striukova, 2004; Ting & Lean, 2009; Zéghal & Anis, 2011). Many periodicals have also been written with the aim of finding an appropriate measurement and representation of such valuable assets in the SOFP of various institutions, giving rise to the frequently interchanged use of the terms intangible assets, intellectual capital and R&D (Marr, Leitner, Schaffhauser-Linzatti, Stowasser, & Wagner, 2005; Rodov & Leliaert, 2002; Swart, 2005). However, since the ISO found the concept of brands as marketing-related intangibles intriguing enough to formulate a standard for its monetary valuation, why not formulate other standards or review the IAS 38 to cater for the representation of brands as an intangible asset in the SOFP? Or, advocate for a separate disclosure of information on such intangible assets?

1.3 Significance of the study

This study is conducted from the accounting perspective using the case of the banking industry in Ghana. It makes contributions that can be used for policy, practice and academic research. The information provided in this study will help government in its policy making on issues concerning the brand of the firms in Ghana. It will also help managers to take a very good look

at the brand of other companies and how they are accounted for before making any merger and acquisition decisions. Still on management, this research will help managers to know how well their brands contribute to their performance.

Academically, this research will be among the few if not the first to research into the accounting aspect of brands in Ghana. It will therefore help broaden the public's knowledge on brands by giving them a different angle of the importance of brand to a firm.

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter gives a brief history of brand measurement and valuation techniques used, based on literature from across the world. Subsequently, literature surrounding the accounting standards and techniques used in the reporting of brand assets are discussed in addition to the challenges encountered by other firms, in disclosing information on their brand values.

2.2 Brand Measurement and Valuation Techniques

Ever since the late 1400s, Fra Luca Piccioli's traditional presentation of financial records which takes into account tangible assets that contribute to the value of the company, still holds; however, in this fast paced economy, where intangible assets reign in amassing wealth for companies, the various stakeholders seek out more information about the investments made in these intangible assets and how best they can benefit from the information.

Hence, spearheading the revolution of presenting the value of their corporate brand on the SOFP in the 1980's, Ranks Hovis McDougall (RHM) Company, paved a way for the influx of brand acquisitions, putting brand valuation techniques in the spotlight and bringing out the value in highly branded companies (Lev, 2001; Seetharaman et al., 2001). Yet, prior to the year 2010, brand valuation techniques used were peculiar to the firms in use of them (Cravens & Guilding, 2001; Moorhouse, 1989; Subramanian, Kalyanasundaram, & Raja, 2009). Thus, due to the varied assumptions underlying the measurements companies use, the need to formulate uniformly accepted valuation method for brands (Treffner, 2011) became urgent, in order to facilitate, accurate comparisons of brand values and the worth of firms in general.

Hence, the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has formulated the Brand Monetary Valuation Method (ISO 10668:2010) in order to have a harmonized method of valuation and to supply companies with a more consistent and reliable approach when measuring brands (Svanberg & Maxén, 2014).

2.2.1 Valuation Methods under ISO 10668

According to Calderón, Cervera, and Mollá (1997) there are two main methods of valuing a brand and they are, the consumer-oriented approach and the asset-oriented approach.

For the purpose of the standard above, focus is placed on the asset-oriented approach, which is further classified into three different approaches namely:

- The Cost Approach
- The Income Approach
- The Market Approach

These approaches as opined by Salinas and Ambler (2009) are influenced by four factors; **market performance, share prices, trading of brands and tax management.**

a) The Cost Approach

This approach consists of all the costs incurred in the acquisition, development and maintenance of a brand and is advisedly used when it is certain that the costs involved can be measured reliably. This approach complies with the normal traditional accounting principles, which tends to focus on the principle of the historical cost concept. Thus, when the cost of a brand is reliably measured, a company can sell off that brand at a value that would be needed to create or develop another brand (Treffner, 2011).

Seetharaman et al. (2001) opines that this approach is disadvantageous; in that, all brand related costs are to be included, irrespective of the time horizon, which is usually difficult to determine.

According to Austin (2007), the difficulty in determining the time horizon of brand related costs is known as the “time gap” and “correlation gap”. The time gap refers to the period of time between when the costs of intangible assets (brands) are incurred and when they begin to exhibit some probable returns or benefits. The correlation gap accounts for why Seetharaman et al. (2006) deems this approach to be weak; that is, the correlation gap implies that there is little or no correlation between the value of intangible and the probable future economic benefit it derives. Austin (2007) and Treffner (2011) have established the underlying weakness to this approach known as “value disappearing” which indicates that the value of resources or money invested (cost) in a brand is always higher than its output value or returns. Moreover, it is problematic, determining the discount rate used to convert all historical costs to their present values; especially, for a matured brand (Svanberg & Maxén, 2014).

Nonetheless, when deciding on an acquisition, a merger or a take-over, a company can use this method as its underpinning measurement tool.

b) The Income Approach

This is considered the most functional and reliable way to determine the value for a brand as it predicts a company’s future economic benefits based on the firm’s net revenue (Gibson, Lee, & Oxley, 2003; Svanberg & Maxén, 2014; Treffner, 2011).

This approach consists of six methods, which are listed below, but not discussed any further.

- The Price Premium Method.
- The Volume Premium Method

- The Relief from Royalty Method
- The Income Split Method
- The Multi-period Excess Earnings Method
- The Incremental Cash Flow Method

c) The Market Approach

Due to the absence of an active market, using this approach might be difficult in that, managers tend to be unable to set trustworthy selling prices for their corporate brands (Austin, 2007; Seetharaman et al., 2001). This approach makes use of quoted prices which are usually set based on the performance of a corporate brand on an active market. Consequently, the absence of an active market renders this method unacceptable or inapplicable in practice.

2.3 Principles and Regulations

Under this section, the recognition (the initial and subsequent measurement), disclosures and their implications on intangible assets reporting are reviewed, in relation to the two main accounting standards underlying this study; IFRS 3 and IAS 38. However, this review is done according to the classifications stipulated in Table 1.

Following the adoption of the IFRS in Ghana, as of 1st January, 2007; every listed company (banks inclusive) is governed by and mandated to have their accounting practices and procedures, comply with both the IFRS and IAS principles.

However, the interpretation of the accounting standards (e.g. IFRS 3 and IAS 38) responsible for the recognition, measurement and disclosure of intangible assets (brands) in an entity's financial statements may differ from one entity to another due to the fact that they are much

more of principles rather than strict rules that must be followed. Due to the differences in interpretation, the validity and ease of comparison of SOFPs worsens, making it difficult for companies with very few tangible assets to value their intangible assets (brands) (Gilbertson & Preston, 2005).

Thus, there are two main principles and regulations (IFRS 3 and IAS 38), that would be discussed; in order to address the recognition, measurement and disclosure of intangibles (brands) in the Statement of Financial Position (SOFP) of a company.

2.3.1 Externally Acquired Intangible (Brand) Assets.

Theories on intangible assets (brands) suggest that, such assets are *interwoven through the fabric* of a firm (Rastogi, 2002), thus, taking the center stage in determining how and why companies generate value over and above their physical and financial resources (Swart, 2005).

Knowing the significance of intangible assets (brands) to a corporate entity, Seetharaman et al. (2001) gathered that whenever an acquisition took place the amount paid was usually higher than the value of the company's net tangible assets. This resulted in goodwill on acquisition, which according to IFRS 3, can be separately presented or identified on the SOFP of the company.

Goodwill as a typical unidentifiable intangible asset, cannot exist independently of the business; thus it cannot be transferred or purchased or sold separately from the business and can consist of a mixture of other intangibles such as brands, copyrights, patents, among others (Seetharaman et al., 2001). Furthermore, Austin (2007)'s studies agrees with Seetharaman et al., in that inasmuch as the fair values of inseparable intangible assets (e.g. brands, patents,

copyrights, etc.) cannot be reliably measured, they can still be presented in the consolidated SOFP, by recognizing them as part of goodwill.

Shifting our attention a bit; the author noticed that, in the case of business combinations, the rules for the recognition of intangible assets (brands) change. In accordance with, IFRS 3 (as revised in 2008) states that, “an acquirer recognizes at the acquisition date, separately from goodwill, an intangible asset of the acquiree, irrespective of whether the asset had been recognized by the acquiree before the business combination”. Thus, in the case of an acquisition, merger or takeover, all intangible assets, including brand values, are recognized by the acquirer or parent entity.

However, this is not the practice of banks in Ghana. To illustrate this point, let us take the merger of The Trust Bank (TTB) and Ecobank Ghana as well as Standard Chartered Bank (SCB) Ghana Limited’s acquisition of the Custody Business from Barclays Ghana Ltd. in 2010. The author compared the financial statements of Ecobank Ghana (2012) to that of SCB Limited (2010) and detected that in the Ecobank’s statements, there was no mention of goodwill gained from the merger, and neither was there any other intangible asset recognized apart from the computer license transferred to the Ecobank group; while that of SCB Ghana Limited, contained the disclosure of intangible assets (reported as ‘other intangibles’), enveloping all intangible assets acquired in the acquisition of the Custody Business.

2.3.1.1 IFRS 3 – Business Combinations

Consequently, IFRS 3 is further delved into to ascertain the extent to which the above literature holds true. IFRS 3 (2008) is the standard responsible for regulating the accounting procedures (the recognition and measurement of acquired assets and liabilities, the determination of goodwill as well as their required disclosures) necessary for recognizing the transactions under

business combinations as well as their effects. It seeks to enhance the relevance, reliability and comparability of information.

A business combination is a transaction in which an acquirer obtains control of one or more businesses and such a transaction should, in accordance with IFRS 3, be accounted for, using the acquisition method, which requires that:

- The acquirer be identified.

IAS 27 and IFRS 10 can be used to identify the acquirer, which is defined as an entity that obtains control of the acquiree.

- The acquisition date should be determined.

The date at which the acquirer legally transfers the consideration to the acquiree (closing date), securing all of its assets and assuming all the liabilities. However, the acquirer can take control over the acquiree before or after the closing date.

- Recognizing and measuring (separately from goodwill) the identifiable assets acquired, the liabilities assumed and any non-controlling interest in the acquiree.
- Recognize goodwill or gain from bargain purchase.

2.3.1.1.1 Recognition, Measurement and Disclosure

- Recognition

Paragraph 13 of IFRS 3 states that in the course of applying the recognition principle: *“As of the acquisition date, the acquirer shall recognize, separately from goodwill, the identifiable assets acquired, the liabilities assumed and any non-controlling interest in the*

acquiree”, some assets and liabilities, previously not recognized as such in the acquiree’s SOFP, may be recognized in the acquirer’s. For example, the acquirer recognizes the acquired identifiable intangible assets, such as a brand name, a patent or a customer relationship or lists, which the acquiree did not recognize as assets in its financial statements because it developed them internally and charged the related costs to expense (EC staff consolidated version as of 18 February 2011).

- Measurement

The measurement principle states that, “The acquirer shall measure the identifiable assets acquired and the liabilities assumed at their acquisition-date fair values.

IAS 36 is a standard for regulating the accounting procedures for the impairment of assets and under this standard, indefinite-life intangibles (which would be referred to as brands for the purpose of this study) are to undergo a fair value impairment test. IFRS 3 defines fair value as “the amount for which an asset could be exchanged or a liability settled, between knowledgeable, willing parties in an arm’s length transaction.”

Furthermore, brands like goodwill are not to be amortized, instead, they are to undergo a **fair value impairment test** for which if there be any impairment recognized, the original value of the brand is reduced by that amount and subsequently valued at the original value, less any impairment costs. Likewise, other limited-life intangible assets acquired at a predetermined cost, is initially recognized at the cost of purchase, and then subsequently assured at the original cost, less its amortized expense.

- Disclosure

IFRS 3 does not explicitly state how intangible assets, specifically, brands are to be disclosed in the SOFP of the acquirer.

2.3.2 Internally Generated Intangible Brand Assets

Characterizing intangibles as assets is the first necessary step to ensuring whether or not brands can be recognized in the SOFP (Otonkue et al., 2009); hence, the development of IAS 38, which caters for the recognition criteria, measurement and disclosure requirements of intangible assets, except for those already addressed in other standards.

IAS 38 primarily defines an intangible asset as *an identifiable non-monetary asset, without any physical substance* which is recognized if:

- It is probable that future economic benefits associated with the asset would flow to the entity.
- The cost of the asset can be measured reliably.

The nature of brand assets meets the first recognition principle but, is a bit shaky with the second; in that, in the case of internally generated brands, all costs in its development phase are expensed in the year it was incurred. Thus, the standard takes the stand that internally generated intangibles are not to be recognized as an asset, but an expense; unless it is generated as is the case of business combination and in accordance with the principles stated under IFRS 3. This can be further attributed to the fact that, expenditure on internally developed brands, mastheads, and customer lists as well as items similar in substance cannot be distinguished from the cost of setting up the business as a whole. Furthermore, due to the unique nature of brand assets, IAS 38 disallows its revaluation, even if it is recognized.

Tollington (1999) and Austin (2007) are however, of the opinion that, in a *Readily Ascertainable Market (RAM)*, costs incurred in developing both internally generated and externally acquired intangibles, brand inclusive, can be capitalized, presented in the financial statements of a company and frequently amortized. For the purposes of this study, an active market is defined as where many buyers and sellers meet in order to trade in homogenous assets, for which their prices are made available to the general public. Together with Subramanian et al. (2009), the authors discovered that some countries such as the US, UK, Australia and Malaysia have formulated their own principles concerning the accounting treatment of intangible assets (brands), based on the guidelines of the IFRS. For example, a *brand asset is treated as a subheading of goodwill in the UK, and is usually written off immediately against reserves upon business acquisition*

According to Zeff and Dharan (1997) and Seetharaman et al. (2001), as long as the brand is specifically identifiable, has a determinate life and not related to a business as a continuing entity; then, the costs involved in developing and maintaining an internally generated brand must be capitalized as an asset. However, due to the challenge of the indefinite life of corporate brand assets coupled with its importance to a going concern, there has to be a well-defined period within which the corporate brand's *life* is considered useful; in order to make it subject to amortization, just as is done with computer software licenses, patents and copyrights. What the author still does not seem to adequately comprehend is that, if capitalizing an asset with a definite, say, ten-year life, is not in violation of the IFRS or IAS or any other accounting standard, why not capitalize the costs incurred in developing an asset with an indefinite-life as well?

To establish the gravity of the question above, take for example, the tax revenues generated by the government of Ghana, through corporate taxes. The government of Ghana in the reading of

the 2016 annual budget declared an increase in the tax percentage to thirty percent (30%). This is good news for the government in that there would be much more tax revenue raked in from the profits made by businesses; but this would mean a reduction in retained earnings of companies in Ghana and possibly the dividends paid out to shareholders. Hence, taking into consideration the growing importance of intangible assets and the fact that IAS 38 states that all investments in intangible assets with an unreliable measurement of cost should be expensed for the period in which it was incurred; the impact the current corporate tax rate is to make from the government's point of view, may not be achieved. This can be attributed to the fact that an increase in expenses of such nature significantly decreases profits, so, why won't firms invest heavily in developing their intangible assets with indefinite lives (brands) rather than the tangible ones; for which there is a 'no' reliable measurement of cost as well as probable generation of future economic benefits?

Furthermore, in addressing the question, Upton (2001) and Austin (2007) are of the opinion that, since the costs incurred are expensed long before the probable benefits are realized, the future benefits of the intangibles cannot be directly traced to the value of the intangible asset. Additionally, even if the value of the brand asset is presented in the financial statements, it will be handled differently depending on how long the purchasing company decides its usefulness (Svanberg & Maxén, 2014). However, companies in Ghana like those in Malaysia are less inclined to recognize the value of brands in their SOFP than their European counterparts would. While brand valuation methods have been popularized in the European countries as well as the U.S. [to the extent that the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) has formulated a standard to aid in the monetary valuation of brands, by companies (ISO 10668)], it has not been a popular issue among Ghanaian banks. This is evidenced by the extent of disclosure of intangible assets in the Statement of Financial Position of the listed banks, which

almost always, is in reference to computer software licenses; hence, the illustration made in table 2, showing the disclosure of intangible assets among the listed banks under study.

Table 2: Recognition of Intangible Assets

Banks Listed on the GSE							
Types of intangibles	Ghanaian Owned (2014)				Foreign (2011, 2012 & 2014)		
	CAL Bank	UT Bank	HFC Bank	GCB Bank	GT Bank	SC Bank	Ecobank
Brand names	—	—	—	—	—	√	—
Copyrights & Patents	—	—	—	—	—	—	—
Software Licenses	√	√	—	√	√	—	√
Goodwill	—	√	√	—	√	√	—

— : non-recognition of intangible asset

√ : recognition of intangible asset

The measurement and reporting of assets of a company do not strictly follow the traditional method of accounting anymore; rather, in order to project future earnings and to make calculated decisions for the future, accountants of today prefer to use value based accounting (Schultz, 2002; Subramanian et al., 2009). This form of accounting for assets just might be a more flexible way to report the value and impact a corporate brand has on a company. However, there is the challenge of brand assets being recognized as more of marketing-related assets rather than financial ones.

Studies conducted by Calderón et al. (1997) show that brand assets from the marketing perspective takes a qualitative approach in terms of associations, preferences and satisfaction whiles the quantitative variables such as profits, market share and costs, are measured from the financial perspective.

Thus, in order to address the dilemma of how to uniformly ascertain the financial value of brand assets, the ISO 10668 was brought to being.

In conclusion, the lack of an open market with comparable products will make the process of gathering accounting values for intangibles slightly different from the traditional measurement of tangible ones (Svanberg & Maxén, 2014). Thus, inasmuch as ISO has formulated the brand monetary valuation method, it is considered insufficient in terms of recognizing the value of brands in financial statements as well as ascertaining both the financial and non-financial impact such a value would have on a company. Thus, IFRS 3 and IAS 38 should be revised in order to inculcate not some, but all underlying principles and accounting treatment of every necessary intangible asset.

CHAPTER 3: METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter focuses on the research methodology used in formation of this research.

First, the underlying assumptions of research methods as well as the specific methodology used in carrying out this study is outlined and explained. Next, it sums-up the sources of data used, as well as how the data acquired displays the recognition, initial and subsequent measurement, disclosure and both financial and non-financial effects of intangible assets (brands) on the performance peculiar to the individual listed banks in Ghana. As such, this chapter talks about the various methods used in the collection of data as well as its analysis. Finally, it will also lay emphasis on the challenges faced in the data collection.

3.2 Research Design

Methodology can be defined as the theory of the methods involved in carrying out a research or throwing more light on a phenomenon (Saunders, Lewis, & Thornhill, 2009). There are two main categories of research methodology namely, the quantitative and the qualitative research.

A qualitative research “begins with assumptions, a worldview, the possible use of a theoretical lens and the study of research problems inquiring into the meaning individuals or groups ascribe to a social or human problem” (Creswell, 2009). It can also be referred to as an effort to understand situations in their uniqueness as part of a particular context (Merriam, 2009; J. L. Patton & Smith, 1989). Qualitative research grows out of three kinds of data collection process namely, in-depth, open-ended interviews, direct observations and both written and audio-visual documents (Creswell, 2009; M. Q. Patton, 2002). This type of research takes into account the participant’s point of view and their diversity (Flick, 2009). The sources of

information mostly adopted under the qualitative method includes observations, interviews, audiovisual material and documents and reports.

Thus, through the lenses of the Ghanaian listed banks, the study examines the reporting techniques used in accounting for their intangible assets by adopting a multiple case study approach (Yin, 2013); in relation to the sample size of the data collected as well as its heavy reliance on publicly available written documents and reports (Guthrie, Petty, Ferrier, & Wells, 1999) from which the author's findings were made.

3.3 Data Collection.

Due to the compliance of listed companies to the preparation of their annual reports according to the IFRS standards, a total sample size of seven banks from the Ghana Stock Exchange, was used in deriving the results of this study.

A content analysis (Guthrie et al., 1999) of the annual reports, specifically, the intangible assets disclosures was performed to determine their effect on both the financial and non-financial performance of the banks. The annual reports were chosen with the intention to determine the trend of intangible asset reporting among the listed banks for a period of five consecutive financial years, being 2009 to 2014. This method of data collection is deemed not to be new as various researches have been conducted in the corporate social, ethical and environmental reporting field of accounting research.

In ascertaining data concerning the effects of intangibles on both financial and non-financial performance of the banks, information was sought from the internet in general.

As part of the collection of data on Ecobank Ghana, a semi-structured interview was conducted (taking into account that they had just celebrated their 25th anniversary) with the finance

director. The semi-structured interviews took an open-ended approach, seeking to address all possible areas of the topic under study as well as to address from the bank's perspective, which intangibles were recognized, valued, if any; as well as the extent to which such intangibles were disclosed in the entity's SOFP.

3.3.1. Limitations

In order to enhance the authenticity of the data collected and analyzed, efforts were made to retrieve some information on the old accounting practices of the Ghanaian banks before the adoption of the IFRS in 2007. However, all efforts proved futile.

Also, in applying an alternative means of gathering data, which is to conduct interviews with corporate finance officers, access to primary data on the extent to which brands or intangibles in general was disclosed in the financial statements as well as other supporting intra-company documents were severely restricted. Thus it was much simpler and productive to extract the needed data from documents made available to the general public on the various banks' websites as well as the annual reports. This challenge faced, may be attributed to the unwillingness of the banks to share 'inside information' on their practices and the fact that the author was constantly referred to the organizations' annual reports during the interviews.

Finally, a challenge was encountered in relation to a banking survey that was used in ascertaining the brand equity of the listed banks. In the use of this tool, the sample size was selected by convenience and from those who volunteered themselves to participate in the interview via publicly posted web links, to postulate a random and diverse population of volunteers. This however rendered very little results while that to the banks rendered little to none. Thus, the questions were set against the various banks' financial statements for the

accounting period ended 31st December, 2014, yielding much more fruitful findings, than in the participation of individuals in the survey study.

CHAPTER FOUR: FINDINGS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the empirical findings obtained from the analysis of the reporting practices and related online documents, which was conducted on Ghanaian samples. These findings indicate that there appears to be a lot of empty rhetoric surrounding the notion of measuring, valuing and reporting on brands in that most of the foreign banks listed on the GSE partake of the world-wide annual banking brand ranking while refraining from making any disclosures on the value and impact their brands have on their banking operations. For example, in the 2014 Top 500 Banking Brands compiled by Brand Finance, the Standard Chartered Bank ranked 10th in the Top10 Ranking of Brand Value in Africa. However, there is no mention of what constitutes its brand value in its Ghanaian annual report.

Since the value of a brand is made up of its strength and dominance in the minds of its customers as well as determining the customer share base, any qualitative information and not necessarily a quantitative one, can go a long way to influence the investment decision of an investor as well as the stock market prices of the bank.

Furthermore, Ecobank Group in the same year was awarded the most influential bank in Africa by Brand Finance and ranked 367th in the Top 500 Banking Brands apart from South Africa. The bank further emerged as the Best Bank in 2014, during the Ghana Banking Awards held on the 29th of August, 2015. In effect, though the foreign listed banks in Ghana tend to comply with the IFRS in that, they do not report on internally generated brand assets domestically. On the international level, they report on such assets through other means such as the annual Banking Brands Ranking by Brand Finance. Table 3 indicates the rankings of the foreign listed banks based on the Brand Finance platform

Table 3: Global Ranking of Best Banking Brands, 2014.

TOP 500 BANKING BRANDS									
RANK 2014	RANK 2013	BRAND	DOMICILE	BRAND VALUE 2014 (\$m)	BRAND RATING 2014	MARKET CAP 2014(\$m)	BRAND VALUE/ MARKET CAP (%)	BRAND VALUE 2013 (\$m)	BRAND RATING 2013
33	33	Standard Chartered	UK	7148	AA+	52,355	14	7022	AA+
367	399	Ecobank	Togo	243	A	1503	16	212	A
422	415	Guaranty Trust	Nigeria	191	AA-	4979	4	201	AA

Source: The Banker/Brand Finance, 2014

Furthermore, the initial strategy for this research was to find out how the seven banks listed on the GSE accounted for their brands through semi-structured interviews. However, that proved to be very difficult. This is because the interviews that were scheduled to take place with the respective banks on the subject did not take place, so the author was forced to rely on only publicly available information. Additionally, in the course of analyzing the annual reports, very little information relating to accounting for brands, was disclosed in them. Thus the focus of the study veered off its planned course. This suggests that the banks lack the sense of accountability in responding to the general public on issues bordering on brands as intangible assets which can be disadvantageous to new investors as well as other stakeholders, such as their customers and stockholders; since they tend to rely heavily on the value relevance of the banks' annual reports (Hùegh-Krohn & Knivsflla, 2000; Stolowy et al., 2001). Value relevance in this case is defined as the ability of financial statements information to both capture and summarizes a firm's value. It is usually measured through the statistical relations between information presented by financial statements and stock market value of returns. Amir and Lev (1996) are of the opinion that in order to make their value relevant decisions, both new and old investors require financial data that includes non-financial information as this can influence their decisions as to which bank's services to patronize as well as used in filling

the gaps created by the traditionally reported accounting book values and the market value of the firm (Amir & Lev, 1996 ; Austin, 2007; Lev, 2001) from which can determine the actual value of returns on their investments.

4.2 Detailed Analysis of Findings

This section seeks to describe in detail, the empirical findings presented in Table 4.

4.2.1 Definition of Variables.

The variables under which the findings are categorized are explained below for better understanding. The term *Intangible assets* are non-physical assets on a company's financial statement, which includes patents, intellectual property, or even something as simple as customer list. This variable helps in classifying the type of intangible asset the bank reports on. The variable *Treatment* refers to how the intangible asset is treated, depending on the classifications made in Table 1 above, where only assets with limited-useful lives are amortized. Thus, amortization refers to a process where the cost or value of an intangible asset is gradually written off or reduced over that asset's useful life and the value amortized is reported as an expense in the income statement to reflect the change on the statement of financial position (SOFP). This concept is similar to depreciation; however, it applies more in the field of intangible assets than tangible ones. The *years* associated with this treatment of intangible assets is usually dependent on the number of years the asset is considered to be useful, depending on the discretion of the entity in use of that asset. Furthermore, as amortization is to intangible assets with definite useful lives, so is the annual impairment test to intangible assets with indefinite useful lives. *IAS 36 is a standard for regulating the accounting procedures for the impairment of assets and under this standard, indefinite-life*

intangibles (which would be referred to as brands for the purpose of this study) are to undergo a fair value impairment test.

The detailed analysis would be done on the basis of banks exhibiting common characteristics in their intangible asset reporting practices. However, if need be, other classifications would be done based on their principal ownership; that is, whether they are foreign or locally owned.

4.2.2 CAL Bank and Ghana Commercial Bank (GCB)

Both banks are domestically owned and operate under the laws of Ghana. They both exhibit similar characteristics in their intangible asset reporting and disclosure. They both only report on software as their intangible assets, and subject it to an amortization for a period of 3 years for GCB and a period of 3-5 years of amortization for CAL Bank. However, none of the software reported on, were internally generated, as they were all externally acquired at a determinable price. Furthermore, prior to 2011, GCB had no report or record on their intangible asset this might be due to their late adoption of the IFRS in their financial reporting. Then, in 2011, the bank decided to reinstate the value attributable to their externally acquired software licenses from 2009 and 2010. Additionally, as part of the banking regulations set by the bank of Ghana, CAL and GCB are required to have a Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) of required capital to total risk-weighted on and off balance sheet assets, of not less than 10%. This made the value of their tier one capital plummet. Thus, reducing their total required capital. However, this did in no way make the CAR any less than is required by the Bank of Ghana.

4.2.3 Ecobank Group

This is a foreign owned bank and has been in operation as long as the GSE has existed. When analyzed, the annual reports provided a qualitative summary on the merger of Ecobank Ghana and The Trust Bank.

“ ... when we merged with The Trust Bank, our main aim was to expand our operations further into the SME and local corporate market... the synergies of the merger... have resulted in phenomenal results for Ecobank for the year 2012.”- Lionel Van Lare Dosoo, Chairman of Ecobank Ghana, 2012 Annual Report.

In reference to the statement above, it can be implied that the bank’s customer base grew bountifully. However, there was no mention, in neither qualitative nor quantitative terms, the value of the customer lists (which is an intangible asset) obtained as a result of the merger.

Inasmuch as the IASB sees no wrong in recognizing the goodwill or bargain purchase obtained from a business combination such as that of EBG and TTB, the bank decided to write goodwill off from the books upon its recognition. This may be due to the type of business combination practiced; which is known as the Business Combination under Common Control (BCUCC).

According to the Statement of Financial Accounting Standards No. 141 the term “common control” is not defined. However, in an attached document, Issue No. 02-5 by the Emerging Issues Task Force (EITF), “common control” exists under the following circumstances:

- An individual or enterprise holds more than 50 percent of the voting ownership interest of each entity.

- Immediate family members hold more than 50 percent of the voting ownership interest of each entity (with no evidence that those family members will vote their shares in any way other than in concert).
 - ❖ Immediate family members include a married couple and their children, but not the married couple's grandchildren.
 - ❖ Entities might be owned in varying combinations among living siblings and their children. Those situations would require careful consideration regarding the substance of the ownership and voting relationships.
- A group of shareholders holds more than 50 percent of the voting ownership interest of each entity, and contemporaneous written evidence of an agreement to vote a majority of the entities' shares in concert exists.

Also, in accordance with the EITF Issue No. 02-5, the pooling of interest method of accounting was used, where the assets and liabilities of the entities involved are not re-measured at fair value, rather the book values of the assets and liabilities of the entities are carried over prospectively from the date of initial acquisition by the parent company. Additionally, over the five-year period under analysis, EBG reported solely on its externally acquired computer software licenses; which was amortized for not more than three years. EBG is also mandated to keep a CAR of not less than 10%, by the central bank of Ghana.

4.2.4 Guaranty Trust Bank (GT Bank)

Being another foreign owned but locally operated bank, GTB is the only one out of the seven listed banks that reports on both its internally and externally generated intangibles, specifically, its computer software licenses. The bank invests heavily in computer software that best suits

its internal processes and interact seamlessly with its core banking procedures. The cost or investment in software is treated as follows:

- Software acquired by the Group is initially stated at cost less accumulated amortization and accumulated impairment losses.
- Subsequently, any expenditure made on software assets is capitalized only when it increases the future economic benefits embodied in the specific asset to which it relates. All other expenditure is expensed as incurred.
- Expenditure on internally developed software is recognized as an asset. However, this is only done when the bank group is able to adequately prove its intent and capability in completing the task as well as being able to measure reliably the cost incurred in its development and finally, measuring the extent to which the software would be able to generate future economic benefits.
- The capitalized costs of internally generated software as well as the associated borrowing costs are amortized over its useful life. Thus they are reported on at capitalized cost less amortization and impairment expenses.
- The intangible asset is amortized for not more than five years.

4.2.5 HFC Bank and UT Bank

From 2009 to 2012, HFC Bank had no record or report on any intangible asset, however, in November 2013, the group acquired three branches and five agencies from Société -Generale Ghana, which resulted in goodwill on acquisition. Thus, in compliance with IFRS 3, the group accounted for and disclosed the value of the goodwill in their SOFP form then onwards. The value of goodwill acquired was subjected to an annual impairment test, for which if there be any loss realized, would reduce the value of the initial cost of goodwill. Furthermore, the

branches acquired, aided in increasing the bank's proximity to its clients as well as significantly increasing their customer base, thus, it can be assumed that, included in the goodwill figure, is the value of the customer list acquired. Moreover, since the bank started to report on their intangibles, the CAR has reduced significantly, from 22.6% in 2013 to 18.98% in 2014. This might tend to discourage further disclosure on their intangible assets.

UT Bank unlike HFC, reported on their intangibles namely their software licenses and goodwill from 2010 through to 2014. The goodwill recognized was as a result of the acquisition of UT Bank Limited by UT Financial Services now UT Bank Ltd. In 2009 however, UT reported only on software licenses, which due to amortization, constantly decreased in value from 2011 through to 2014. Furthermore, the goodwill acquired as a result of the business combination is allocated to three individual cash generating units (CGU), namely corporate banking, retail banking and treasury, for the purposes of impairment testing.

4.2.6 Standard Chartered Bank (SCB)

Standard Chartered Bank Group, between October and December 2010 acquired the Custody Business of Barclays Bank, across various locations in Africa, Ghana inclusive; thus recognizing a total goodwill of \$21 million (SCB Annual Report, 2010). However, the notes of the Ghanaian Subsidiary bank in the same year, indicated that, goodwill realized on the acquisition of the Custody business, Ghana was nil, implying that the acquisition of the custody business from Barclays Ghana, contributed nothing to the group, in terms of the total goodwill recognized by the group in the same year.

Also, pertaining to the acquisition of the custody business in Ghana, the disclosure of "other intangible assets" was not detailed as to what exactly constituted the value of the other intangibles, reported in their financial statement. It was however stated that this classification

was to represent the fair value of the custody business acquired and was subjected to an eight-year amortization period.

Furthermore, during 2009, the Group acquired a further 2 percent interest in its subsidiary in Ghana, for an additional \$8 million, generating goodwill of \$6 million. However, this was not reported in the Ghanaian 2009 nor 2010 annual reports.

Table 4 presents a tabular summary of the chronological findings on the analysis of intangible asset (brand) reporting practices from the annual reports among the seven listed banks.

Table 4: Findings from the annual reports

Banks and Year	Variables	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014
CAL Bank	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	Software Amortization Purchased	Software Amortization 3-5 purchased	Software Amortization 3-5 Purchased	Software Amortization 3-5 Purchased	Software Amortization 3-5 Purchased	Software Amortization 3-5 Purchased
Ecobank Ghana	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	Software Amortization Depreciated 3 Purchased	Software Amortization 3 Purchased	Software Amortization Not more than 3 Purchased	Software (TTB) Amortization 3 Purchased	Software Amortization 3 Purchased	Software Amortization 3 Purchased
GCB Bank	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	No info	No info	Software licenses Amortization 3 Purchased	Software licenses Amortization Not more than 3 Purchased	Software licenses Amortization Not more than 3 Purchased	Software licenses Amortization Not more than 3 Purchased
Guarantee Trust Bank	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	Software Amortization 5 Both	Software Amortization 5 Both	Software Amortization 5 Both	Software Amortization 5 Both	Software Amortization 5 Both	Software Amortization 5 Both
HFC Bank	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	No info	No info	No info	No info	Goodwill Impairment Purchased	Goodwill Impairment Purchased
Standard Chartered Bank	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	Software Amortization 3-5 purchased	Software, Goodwill and other intangibles Amortization 8 purchased	Software, Goodwill and other intangibles Amortization purchased	Software, and other intangibles Amortization purchased	Software, and other intangibles Amortization purchased	Software, and other intangibles Amortization Purchased
UT Bank	<i>Intangible Asset:</i> <i>Treatment:</i> <i>Years of treatment:</i> <i>Category:</i>	Software Amortization 3-5 purchased	Software & Goodwill Amortization and impairment 3-5 purchased	Software & Goodwill Amortization and impairment 3-5 purchased	Software & Goodwill Amortization and impairment 3-5 purchased	Software & Goodwill Amortization and impairment 3-5 purchased	Software & Goodwill Amortization and impairment 3-5 purchased

CHAPTER 5: IMPLICATIONS, SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter seeks to find the possible areas of effect the findings in chapter four could have on the listed banks. The implications would be broadly categorized into two; namely financial and non-financial implications. The financial implication is further be categorized into tax implications and effects on the capital adequacy of the firm; and the non-financial implications are also further grouped into social and socio-economic implications.

5.1.1 Financial implications.

This sub-section refers to the extent to which the intangible asset reporting practices of the listed banks affect their financial wellbeing. The section is sub-categorized into:

5.1.1. A. Tax Implications

It was afore mentioned that intangible assets that cannot be separately identified (e.g. corporate brand assets) are usually included in the goodwill value of an acquiree, when it is purchased. Thus, mergers and acquisitions (as in the cases of Ecobank, SCB-Ghana, UT Bank and HFC) have considerable tax implications which require careful considerations during the purchase price allocation (PPA). PPA refers to the allocation of the purchase consideration of a business to the various assets and liabilities acquired. Thus, to the acquiree, a high value of goodwill can imply a substantial gain from the sale transaction. This in tax is called capital gains, which in Ghana, is subject to a tax rate of 15%. This might be an incentive for various target businesses to refrain from developing their intangible asset base. Furthermore, to an acquirer, a PPA that leans more towards tangible assets in an acquisition is much more favorable in that,

tangible assets are depreciable assets, which in Ghana, is almost always subject to some capital allowance rate, depending on the class of assets it falls into. Capital allowance is a mechanism, which replaces the function of depreciation, for tax purposes. This reduces the amount of tax payable on the value of one's tangible assets. This tax implication diminishes the incentive of the listed banks, from increasing their investments in other intangibles, other than the computer software licenses.

5.1.1. B. Effects on the Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR)

The Bank of Ghana (BoG) is the body responsible for the regulatory practices of the various banks operating in Ghana. As such, the CAR is set to ensure that banks have more than enough capital to offset any risks that are associated with their on and off-balance sheet assets. The minimum regulatory capital requirement is set at GHC 60 million with a ratio of total capital to total risk-weighted assets (those on and off the financial statements) of not less than 10%. In the light of this, the banks are mandated to calculate and report on their regulatory capital which is divided into two tiers. However, for the purposes of this studies, the components of Tier 1 capital, only, is delved into. One key component is the element of intangible asset which is deducted from the total of shareholder's capital and reserves other than regulatory reserves; along with other deductions such as investments in subsidiaries. The intangible assets value is deducted in order to ensure that the bank is adequately capitalized given a range of stress events. However, this can cause a severe decline in the CAR, given an increase in the value of intangible asset of a business. Thus, even though reporting on intangibles may increase the value of the bank's total assets, making the bank seem more solvent or liquid, in truth, which might not be the case, as it is not considered as part of the regulatory capital base. Furthermore, in this way, when liquidity or solvency ratios are being determined, they represent the true reflection of the sustenance of the business. However, this can also dissuade the banks from

reporting on their intangible assets as a capitalized asset rather than an expense written off in the income statement; if after all the effort put into reporting it, it is not taken into consideration when determining the capital base.

5.1.2 Non-Financial Implications

This section seeks to explore some non-financial implications of the inadequate disclosure of the listed firm's intangible assets. The section is further grouped into two subsections namely, socio-economic implications and social implications.

5.1.2 A Socio-Economic Implications

The Ghanaian listed banks form an intrinsic part of the capital market of the economy. Thus, one major consequence of the meager disclosures of intangible assets in the SOFP of the listed banks, is the misallocation of resources in the capital market. Generally, investing in intangible assets is risky. That is why, any investment in such assets, requires that there be adequate disclosures on them, in order to attenuate the fears of the investors, as the inability of management to do so, may lead to an increase in the cost of capital of the firm's stocks. An increase in the cost of capital implies an increase in the rate of return, required by the investors; which would deplete the banks' reserved resources. It is the author's believe that it is for this very reason that the foreign listed banks partake of the annual best banking brand award, held by the Brand Finance.

Also, inadequate reporting on their intangible assets leads to information asymmetry between internal and external stakeholders of the listed banks. Information asymmetry occurs when the internal stakeholders of the listed banks, possess an information, that would enhance the chances of restructuring his or her portfolio as and when needed to diminish the chances of

making losses. This is usually to the detriment of the external stakeholders, as they may not be privy to such important

5.1.2 B Social Implications

The banks have to put in place different structures to ensure that the different needs and interests of their diversified clientele is met. Based on the extent of investment the banks make in developing and purchasing their computer software, it can be implied that the level of customer interaction and satisfaction in the industry has increased significantly. As their customer base and clientele become diverse in geographical location, development and race wise, the need to increase investment in this socially and technically important intangible arises. It is important to build up on this intangible asset due to the increasing demand for security and confidentiality of account information as well as on the other services provided (the use of heightened security precautions become necessary). Furthermore, the increase in demand for 'banking on the go' and internet banking have greatly influenced the investment decisions of the banks in relation to the computer software licenses that are both internally developed as well as acquired.

5.2 Summary of findings and implications

It is evident from Table 4 that, the computer software license is the most reported and disclosed intangible across all seven banks. Even Ghana Commercial Bank (GCB) that initially did not recognize any intangibles at all in the years ended 2009 and 2010, started recording their values of this intangible from 2011 as well as re-instating the computer software value from the cost of computers stated in the plant, property and equipment (Rodov & Leliaert) schedule from 2009. Since most banks are leaning towards internet banking, in a wake to maximize the banking experience of their customers (as these are the life-blood of the banks) it may be the

reason for the countless disclosures of computer software licenses in the SOFP. Another reason for disclosing computer software in their annual report can be attributed to the bank's willingness to inform their customers on the regularity of how they upgrade their systems of operations (especially, the banking software which is a major part of the daily operations of the banks). This tends to increase the sense of security the customers have in their banks.

It was also discovered that internally generated intangibles were not recorded in the annual reports of the listed banks with the exception of the Guaranty Trust Bank (GTB). GTB capitalized both its internally developed and externally acquired software for all five years, suggesting that, their level of innovation with respect to intangible assets is well above all the other listed banks. It is of the author's opinion that the cost of acquiring intangibles (computer software) externally could be more expensive than generating such software internally. This is due to excess costs like, transportation and transactional costs. Albeit, this may not always be the case in the sense that, at certain instances the cost of acquiring the software externally may be less expensive. For example, the 'spare capacity'- skilled labor, office space, time and monetary resources - of the bank being used in developing and implementing the software might generate a higher level of costs, relative, to purchasing it. Here, the cost-benefit of the intangible asset is analyzed between a make or buy decision of the firm. If it is more feasible to buy rather than to internally develop, the bank can go ahead and do that. This may suggest the reason why most of the listed banks are acquiring their software externally.

One other intangible asset recognized in the SOFPs was Goodwill. This value did not represent internally generated goodwill, but externally acquired goodwill. Standard Chartered Bank Ghana Limited in the acquisition of the Custody Business from Barclays Bank Ghana Limited in 2010, recognized goodwill and the value of other intangibles acquired. There were also a number of acquisitions and mergers such as; HFC Bank acquiring 3 branches and 5 agencies

from Société-Generale, Ecobank (EBG) merging with The Trust Bank (TTB) and UT Bank acquiring UT Bank Limited; which did not necessarily lead to the recognition of goodwill arising from the business combinations. UT Bank and HFC, separately recognized the value of their goodwill in their SOFP. Also, all disclosures on goodwill indicated that, it is reviewed annually and tested for impairment; for which if there be any impairment loss, the value of goodwill is reduced by such an amount. The computer software license on the other hand is amortized and treated at cost less amortization and any impairment loss, for not less than 3 years and not more than 5 years.

Furthermore, as part of ascertaining the capital adequacy ratio (CAR), banks and financial institutions are required by the Central Bank, to have a prescribed ratio of total capital to total risk-weighted assets of not less than 10%. This CAR is divided into two tiers, out of which the Tier 1 capital is ascertained by deducting the total value of intangible assets and investment in other businesses, from the Shareholder's fund (Ordinary shares plus Disclosed Reserves). This implies that, the higher the value of intangible assets capitalized and not expensed, the lower the value of the Tier 1 capital requirement, being in violation of the regulations stated by the Central Bank of Ghana and of the Banking Act 2004, Act 673. This probably may account for the reason why only a few intangible assets are accounted for and disclosed in the banks' financial statements. It also implies that the CAR Tier 1 capital requirement does not reflect the true value of the listed banks.

5.3 Recommendations

The Ghana Stock Exchange in conjunction with the Bank of Ghana can aid the listed banks, by formulating and implementing policies that would allow them to include the value of the firm's intangible assets, given a set of risk measures, in the calculation of their tier 1 capital of the

CAR. This would show a truer state of the risks faced by the individual banks and how best such risks are deflected in order to prevent a negative effect on shareholder's wealth.

Likewise, the listed banks can advocate for the option of voluntarily disclosing non-financial or specific information (Amir & Lev, 1996 ; Beattie, McInnes, & Fearnley, 2004; Lev, 2003; OECD, 2006a, 2006b; Stolowy et al., 2001; Zéghal & Anis, 2011), concerning the intangible assets they invest in. This would greatly improve the value relevance of their annual reports and fill in the correlation gap created by the conservatism principle of accounting (Austin, 2007; Liang & Yao, 2005; Monahan, 2005; Upton, 2001). Further research can also be conducted in determining the role internal disclosures of intangible assets play in the making of managerial decisions and the relevance of brand values to intangible asset – intensive firms, such as telecommunication companies, in the developing country's context, given the economic conditions peculiar to developing economies.

5.3.1 Conclusion

It has become the mantra of every listed bank to claim compliance with the International Financial Reporting Standards and do not clearly disclose what they mean when that is stated. However, those that exhibited a level of understanding to the intangible asset reporting standards also disclosed, at the local level, very little information on their intangible asset other than what is generally used across all seven banks. The border lines of the value proposition or relevance of the individual banks are gradually fading out as the practices begin to experience the growing importance or need of disclosing more information on the value of their intangible assets and the effect of such on the value of the firm, as well as how it contributes to the creation of the shareholder's wealth.

Albeit, the banks, investors and securities market in Ghana are not ready or well equipped to inculcate the value and impact of intangible asset reporting in their operations or activities. The banks must be encouraged to challenge the status quo in order to enhance both their internal and external reporting values.

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